

Comparative Analysis of Qualitative And Quantitative Research

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Abstract

There's no hard and fast rule for qualitative versus quantitative research, and it's often taken for granted. It is claimed here that the divide between qualitative and quantitative research is ambiguous, incoherent, and hence of little value, and that its widespread use could have negative implications. This conclusion is supported by a variety of arguments. Qualitative researchers, for example, have varying perspectives on fundamental problems (such as the use of quantification and causal analysis), which makes the difference as such shaky. In addition, many elements of qualitative and quantitative research overlap significantly, making it difficult to distinguish between the two. Practically in the case of field research, the Qualitative and quantitative approach can't be distinguished clearly as the study pointed. The distinction may limit innovation in the development of new research methodologies, as well as cause complication and wasteful activity. As a general rule, it may be desirable not to conceptualise research approaches at such abstract levels as are done in the context of qualitative or quantitative methodologies. Discussions of the benefits and drawbacks of various research methods, rather than general research questions, are recommended.

Keywords: Research, Qualitative Research, Quantitative Research, Definition, Characteristics, Advantages, Disadvantages, Comparison

1. Introduction:

In educational research, the paradigm war has been on for more than 50 years over quantitative versus qualitative research methodologies. There was a strong desire in the late twentieth century to preserve one of the methods as supreme. Combining both methodologies into one study or series of studies is becoming more commonplace as of the beginning of the twenty-first century. Despite these indicators of development, novice educational researchers are still unsure of how to use the proper research approach at the right moment. As a result, this paper offers helpful advice for deciding between quantitative and qualitative research in educational research.

2. Research and Types of Research:

To put it simply, research is a thorough and meticulous inquiry into a particular field. It has significant importance in various fields, such as business, economics and politics. Research is conducted to serve a diverse range of purposes, such as enhancing the knowledge of the researcher, developing theories and revising facts. Additionally, it aids in locating a problem's fundamental source and developing creative solutions. According to John W. Creswell (2008), research is a process of steps used to collect and analyze information to increase our understanding of a topic or issue. Research may be classified into different types for the sake of better understanding of the concept. Several bases can be adopted for classification such as nature of data, branch of knowledge, extent of coverage, place of investigation, method employed, time frame and so on.

The basic types of research are as follows:

- (1) Types of Research according to its Application
 - Basic or Fundamental or Pure
 - Applied
- (2) Types of Research according to its Objectives
 - Descriptive
 - Explanatory
 - Exploratory
- (3) **Types of Research according to its Approach**
 - **Quantitative**
 - **Qualitative**
- (4) Others types of Research
 - Action
 - Historical
 - Longitudinal
 - Conceptual
 - Empirical etc...

In this project only the comparative analysis of approach based researches i.e. Qualitative and Quantitative researches are discussed.

3. Qualitative and Quantitative Research:

Both qualitative and quantitative methods of user research play important roles in research development. Data from quantitative research—such as sample size, demographics, and user preferences—provides important information for research formulation and area selection. Qualitative research provides valuable data for designing research—including data about user needs, behaviour patterns, and use cases. (Madrigal & McClain, 2012)

3.1. Definitions:

When collecting and analyzing data, quantitative research deals with numbers and statistics, while qualitative research deals with words and meanings. Both are important for gaining different kinds of knowledge (Streefkerk, 2019).

- (i) **Qualitative Research** - Qualitative research is a scientific method of observation to gather non-numerical data. This type of research refers to the meaning, concepts, definition, characteristics, metaphors, symbols and description of things and not their counts or measures.
 - **Ways (2011)** - *“An approach used to gain an understanding of underlying reasons, opinions and motivations. It provides insights into the problem or helps to develop ideas or hypothesis for potential quantitative research.”*

- **Denzin & Lincoln (2011)** - *“Qualitative research is multimethod in focus, involving an interpretative, naturalistic approach to its subject matter. This means that qualitative researchers study things in their natural settings, attempting to make sense of, or interpret, phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them. Qualitative research involves the studied use and collection of a variety of empirical materials – case study, personal experience, introspective, life story, interview, observational, historical, interactional, and visual texts – that describe routine and problematic moments and meanings in individuals’ lives.”*
 - **Keith Punch (1998)** defined Qualitative research as *“empirical research where data are not in the form of numbers”*. Empirical means that data or research is based on something that is experienced or observed as opposed to being based on theory. Data could be in the form of videos, images, or artefacts.
 - *“Qualitative research involves any research that uses data that do not indicate ordinal values.”* (Paul Nchoji Nkwi, Nyamongo, & Gery Wayne Ryan, 2001)
 - *“Qualitative research is a research methodology which deals with understanding human beliefs, behaviour, values and perceptions of certain social or non-social issues within their own environmental contexts. It makes use of open-ended questions and motivates participants to express their thoughts and views openly with no limitations.”* (Voxco, 2018)
- (ii) Quantitative Research** - Quantitative research is the systematic empirical investigation of observable phenomena via statistical, mathematical or computational techniques. The objectives of quantitative research is to develop and employ mathematical models, theories and hypothesis pertaining to phenomena.
- **Ways (2011)** - *“An approach, quantify problems by generating numerical data or information that can be transformed into usable statistics.”*
 - *“Quantitative methodology is the dominant research framework in the social sciences. It refers to a set of strategies, techniques and assumptions used to study psychological, social and economic processes through the exploration of numeric patterns.”* (Coghlan & Brydon-Miller, 2014)
 - **Bryman (2016)** - *“Quantitative research is a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. It is formed from a deductive approach where emphasis is placed on the testing of theory, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies.”*
 - *“Quantification clarifies issues which qualitative analysis leaves fuzzy. It is more readily contestable and likely to be contested. It sharpens scholarly discussion, sparks off rival hypotheses, and contributes to the dynamics of the research process.”* - **Angus Maddison** (The Interaction Design Foundation, n.d.)

3.2. Characteristics:

3.2.1. Characteristics of Qualitative Research:

Some distinctive characteristics of qualitative research are:

- (i) Qualitative research methodology provides real-time data as it is carried out at the exact time of the issues that participants are facing.
- (ii) Qualitative research provides first-hand reliable data as it is conducted in the participants' environment.
- (iii) It can make use of various available data gathering sources such as interviews, focus groups, case study and so on to provide all kinds of information.
- (iv) Qualitative research makes the understanding of the research topic easy by breaking it down into small detailed inferences and studying it individually.
- (v) Participants tend to build trust with the researcher and provide real and unaltered information without any hesitation.
- (vi) Qualitative researchers require to describe the cause and factors behind a phenomenon understanding the reasons behind it.
- (vii) Qualitative research allows minimum involvement of the researcher, hence eliminating the researcher biases from the results.
- (viii) It is participant-oriented where the researcher should work to bring out what people think and not what other researchers and observers think.

3.2.2. Characteristics of Quantitative Research:

Some distinctive characteristics of quantitative research are:

- (i) Structured tools: Structured tools such as surveys, polls, or questionnaires are used to gather quantitative data. Using such structured methods helps in collecting in-depth and actionable data from the survey respondents.
- (ii) Sample size: Quantitative research is conducted on a significant sample size that represents the target market. Appropriate sampling methods have to be used when deriving the sample to fortify the research objective
- (iii) Close-ended questions: Closed-ended questions are created per the objective of the research. These questions help collect quantitative data and hence, are extensively used in quantitative research.
- (iv) Prior studies: Various factors related to the research topic are studied before collecting feedback from respondents.
- (v) Quantitative data: Usually, quantitative data is represented by tables, charts, graphs, or any other non-numerical form. This makes it easy to understand the data that has been collected as well as prove the validity of the market research.
- (vi) Generalization of results: Results of this research method can be generalized to an entire population to take appropriate actions for improvement.

3.3. Pros/Advantages/Benefits

In this section several advantages of qualitative and quantitative research are worth reviewing when there is a hypothesis under consideration. (Miller, 2018a) (Miller, 2018b)

3.3.1. Pros of Qualitative Research

List of the Pros of Qualitative Research...

- (i) It provides more content that is useful for practical application.

- (ii) It uses a smaller sample size than other research methods.
- (iii) It offers the chance to develop specific insights.
- (iv) It eliminates the potential for bias within the data.
- (v) It can be an open-ended process.
- (vi) It turns individual experiences into usable data.
- (vii) It uses a fluid operational structure instead of rigid guidelines.
- (viii) It focuses on the purpose of a decision instead of the details.
- (ix) It still offers a predictive quality.
- (x) It is more affordable than other research methods.

3.3.2. Pros of Quantitative Research

List of the Pros of Quantitative Research...

- (i) The quantitative approach allows you to reach a higher sample size.
- (ii) You can collect information quickly when using quantitative research.
- (iii) Quantitative research uses randomized samples.
- (iv) Results duplication is possible when using quantitative research.
- (v) Quantitative research can focus on facts or a series of information.
- (vi) The research performed with the quantitative approach is anonymous.
- (vii) Quantitative research doesn't require direct observation to be useful.

3.4. Cons/Disadvantages/Limitations

In this section several disadvantages of qualitative and quantitative research are worth reviewing when there is a hypothesis under consideration. (Miller, 2018a) (Miller, 2018b)

3.4.1. Cons of Qualitative Research

List of the Cons of Qualitative Research...

- (i) It creates subjective data.
- (ii) It takes a lot of time to collect the data points.
- (iii) It does not offer statistical representation.
- (iv) It requires researchers to be knowledgeable about what they are reviewing.
- (v) It requires researchers to identify unspoken data points.
- (vi) It may require repetitive research efforts.
- (vii) It is challenging to replicate results using this method.
- (viii) It can be subjective to research influence.
- (ix) It does not offer data rigidity.

3.4.2. Cons of Quantitative Research

List of the Cons of Quantitative Research...

- (i) This method doesn't consider the meaning behind social phenomena.
- (ii) Every answer provided in this research method must stand on its own.
- (iii) Quantitative research sometimes creates unnatural environments.
- (iv) Some efforts at randomization will not create usable information.
- (v) There is no access to specific feedback.

- (vi) Quantitative research studies can be very expensive.
- (vii) Answer validity always creates a cloud of doubt on the final results.
- (viii) Individual characteristics don't always apply to the general population.

4. Comparative Analysis between Qualitative and Quantitative Research:

It is abstract, highly general, and generally accepted that there is a difference between qualitative and quantitative research. This project aims to demonstrate that the divide between qualitative and quantitative research is murky, inadequate, and hence of low use and that its popularity runs the risk of having unfavourable effects. After analyzing a handful of research papers and thoughts of several prominent persons, the differences of Qualitative and Quantitative researches pointed out in following thematic divisions. (Allwood, 2011; Creswell, 2008; Humphrey, n.d.; Madrigal & McClain, 2012; Raghunath, 2016; Surbhi, 2018; Wagle, 2018)

4.1. Differences in the Concept:

- **Qualitative Research** is primarily exploratory research. It is used to gain an understanding of underlying reasons, opinions, and motivations. It provides insights into the problem or helps to develop ideas or hypotheses for potential quantitative research.
- **Quantitative Research** is used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. It is used to quantify attitudes, opinions, behaviors, and other defined variables – and generalize results from a larger sample population.

4.2. Differences in the Meaning:

- **Qualitative research** is a method of inquiry that develops understanding on human and social sciences, to find the way people think and feel.
- **Quantitative research** is a research method that is used to generate numerical data and hard facts, by employing statistical, logical and mathematical technique.

4.3. Differences in the View Point of Researcher:

- **Qualitative research** is the research where researcher relies on the views of the participants,
- **Quantitative research** is the research where researcher decides what to do and what not to.

4.4. Differences in Relationship with the studied environment:

- **Qualitative:** (active subject) Naturalistic approach: space and actions are analyzed in the present time during the research.
- **Quantitative:** (passive subject) Experimental approach: the subject is not responsive but this is not a problem.

4.5. Differences in Interaction researcher/respondent:

- **Qualitative** : Essential, it is necessary that empathy arises between the two parts.
- **Quantitative** : Almost absent, the interviewer must be warm and human but must not interact outside the questionnaire.

4.6. Differences in Depth of Research:

- **Qualitative research** studies are more in-depth yet focused on smaller areas,

- **Quantitative research** studies cover a broader range of topics under the main research topic but are less in-depth in comparison to qualitative studies.

4.7. Differences in Objective:

- The objectives of **qualitative research** is to explore and discover ideas used in the ongoing processes.
- The objectives of **quantitative research** is to examine cause and effect relationship between variables.

4.8. Differences in the data:

In terms of the actual data, here are some of the key differences:

- **Qualitative** data is not countable. It's chunks of text, photos, videos, and so on. **Quantitative** data can be counted as it's numerical.
- **Qualitative** data is usually unstructured, which means it's not ordered or grouped logically. Researcher can turn qualitative data into structured **quantitative** data through analysis methods like coding.
- **Qualitative** data is quite rich, and can give you directional insights about people's thoughts, feelings, emotions, and so on. **Quantitative** data can help to give researcher more confidence about a trend, and allow researcher to derive numerical facts.

4.9. Differences between Rich, deep data data vs Hard, reliable:

- **Qualitative researcher** claim, by contrast, that contextual approach and their often prolonged involvement in a setting engender rich data.
- **Quantitative data** are often depicted as 'hard' in the sense of being robust and unambiguous, owing to the precision offered by measurement.

4.10. Differences in the data collection methods:

- **Qualitative data** collection methods vary using unstructured or semi-structured techniques. Some common methods include focus groups (group discussions), individual interviews, and participation/observations.
- **Quantitative data** collection methods are much more structured than Qualitative data collection methods. Quantitative data collection methods include various forms of surveys – online surveys, paper surveys, mobile surveys and kiosk surveys, face-to-face interviews, telephone interviews, longitudinal studies, website interceptors, online polls, and systematic observations.

4.11. Differences in Response :

- **Qualitative research** studies generally have open-ended questions and therefore open-ended, unstructured responses.
- On the other hand, **quantitative research** studies have more structured and fixed questions and hence, similar responses.

4.12. Differences in the Sample Size :

- Most of the time **qualitative data** will be collected from a smaller sample size than quantitative data, because generally researcher are not looking for statistical significance with qualitative research.
- **Quantitative data** generally collected form a larger quantity of sample size.

4.13. Differences in Focus of Research :

- **Qualitative research** is purely text-based while,

- *Quantitative research* is focused primarily on numbers.
- 4.14. Differences in Statistical Tests :**
- *Qualitative research* makes use of no statistical tests for the analysis aspect,
 - while *quantitative research* uses statistical tests heavily in the analysis phase.
- 4.15. Differences in Hypothesis Formulation:**
- In *qualitative research* hypothesis are generated from the collected data
 - In *quantitative research* hypothesis are tested from the collected data.
- 4.16. Differences in Scientific Method of Research:**
- In *qualitative research* scientific method of research is Exploratory i.e. bottom-up, where new hypothesis or theories are generated from the collected data
 - In *quantitative method* of research scientific method of research is Confirmatory i.e. top-down, where the researcher will test hypothesis from the collected data
- 4.17. Differences in Generalisations:**
- *Qualitative research* which is based on text is less generalisable,
 - *Quantitative research*, based on numbers is more generalisable.
- 4.18. Differences in Uniformity of the detection instrument :**
- *Qualitative Research* : Absent. Not necessarily always the same.
 - *Quantitative Research* : It is necessary to use a standard.
- 4.19. Differences in Communication of Findings :**
- *Qualitative Research* : Organisation more descriptive and narrative in nature.
 - *Quantitative research* : Organisation more analytical in nature, drawing inferences and conclusions, and testing magnitude and strength of a relationship.
- 4.20. Differences in Reasoning Method :**
- *Qualitative research* follows Inductive reasoning method (looking for emergence of any theory) i.e. Starts from **Observation**, then we find out the **Pattern**, make the **Tentative hypothesis** and finally form the **Theory**
 - *Quantitative research* follows Deductive reasoning method (fitting data in theories) i.e. Starts from the **Theory**, from which we form **Hypothesis**, make the **Observation** and finally confirm our **Hypothesis**.
- 4.21. Differences in Sampling Techniques :**
- In *qualitative research* sampling is mostly ‘non-random sampling’.
 - In *quantitative research* Sampling is mostly ‘random sampling’.
- 4.22. Differences in Information Diversity :**
- *Qualitative research* gives more information of limited cases.
 - *Quantitative research* gives limited information of more cases.
- 4.23. Differences in Research study:**
- In *qualitative research* study of the whole subject is done.
 - In *quantitative research* only specific variables are studied here.
- 4.24. Differences in Time Expenditure:**

- **Qualitative research:** Time expenditure lighter on the planning end and heavier during the analysis phase
- **Quantitative research:** Time expenditure heavier on the planning phase and lighter on the analysis phase

4.25. Differences in dependency of validity and reliability of research:

- **Qualitative research** can be valid and reliable : largely depends on skill and rigor of the researcher
- **Quantitative research** can be valid and reliable : largely depends on the measurement device or instrument used

4.26. Differences in Scope of results:

- **Qualitative research:** Limited number of cases.
- **Quantitative research:** Significant number, representativity.

4.27. Differences in Research Result :

- **Qualitative research** : Develops initial understanding.
- **Quantitative research** : Recommends final course of action.

5. Conclusion:

Research is the most widely used tool to increase and brush-up the stock of knowledge about something and someone. In the field of marketing, business, sociology, psychology, science & technology, economics, etc. there are two standard ways of conducting research, i.e. qualitative research or quantitative research. While the qualitative research relies on verbal narrative like spoken or written data, the quantitative research uses logical or statistical observations to draw conclusions. Lastly, the methods used in qualitative research are in-depth interviews, focus groups, etc. In contrast, the methods of conducting quantitative research are structured interviews and observations. Qualitative Research develops the initial understanding whereas quantitative research recommends a final course of action.

This two methods of research cannot be compared side by side but for the purposes of trying to understand some key characteristics of each of the types of research, in this paper we looked at qualitative and quantitative methods and how they might complement one another (Physiopedia, n.d.).

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